

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in (-), zoom out (+), dropdown menu (MtrunA17Chr0c01), text input (MtrunA17Chr0c01:97081..98486 (1.4)), Go button, and icons for CC, CHG, CHH.

97,250	97,500	97,750	98,000	98,250	98,500
Zoom in to see sequence					

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP3: MtrunA17_Chr1g0148371

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls (back, forward, zoom in, zoom out) and a search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr1' and 'MtrunA17Chr1:1782126..1789155 (7) Go'. Includes icons for CC, CHG, and CHM.

1,782,500 1,783,750 1,785,000 1,786,250 1,787,500 1,788,750

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP4: MtrunA17_Chr1g0149991

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: Left arrow, Right arrow, Zoom out (-), Zoom in (+), Search (M), and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr1" and "MtrunA17Chr1:3085631..3092660 (7) Go".

Reference sequence track: 1. Reference sequence. Includes zoom controls and labels for coordinates: 3,086,250, 3,087,500, 3,088,750, 3,090,000, 3,091,250, 3,092,500.

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP6: MtrunA17_Chr1g0152521

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:5229546..5233178 (3) Go

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0152521
Putative rossmann-like alpha/beta/alpha sandwich, methionyl/Leucyl tRNA synthetase

MtrunA17_Chr1R0022700

MtrunA17_Chr1R0022710

CP7: MtrunA17_Chr1g0153001

Navigation controls including left and right arrows, zoom in/out icons, a search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr1', and a coordinate field showing 'MtrunA17Chr1:5598651..5602960 (4)'. There are also icons for CC, CNG, and CDM.

5,598,750 5,600,000 5,601,250 5,602,500

1. Reference sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP8: MtrunA17_Chr1g0155251

...nA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

SSRP1, MtrunA17_Chr1g0155251

Putative chromatin remodeling & transcriptional activation HMG family

CP9: MtrunA17_Chr1g0158341

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:9327979..9329897 (1) Go

28,000 9,328,500 9,329,000 9,329,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP10: MtrunA17_Chr1g0162101

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:12120190..12122947 Go

12,120,500 12,121,000 12,121,500 12,122,000 12,122,500

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0162101
putative protein

MtrunA17_Chr1R0056910

MtrunA17_Chr1R0056920

MtrunA17_Chr1R0056930

CP11: MtrunA17_Chr1g0164591

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr1" and "MtrunA17Chr1:14352206..14359235".

14,352,500 14,353,750 14,355,000 14,356,250 14,357,500 14,358,750

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP12: MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:29906783..29911406 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1R0170160
MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361
putative protein

CP13: MtrunA17_Chr1g0181761

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:32738523..32743280 Go

32,738,750 32,740,000 32,741,250 32,742,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0181761
Putative ribosomal protein L4/L1e

MtrunA
Putat

CP14: MtrunA17_Chr1g0182591

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search. Search bar: MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:33495020..33513814 Go. Download, Print, CC, CHG, CHH icons.

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP15: MtrunA17_Chr1g0183001

CP16: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:36151945..36155113 Go

36,152,000 36,152,500 36,153,000 36,153,500 36,154,000 36,154,500 36,155,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP17: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:36151945..36155113 Go

36,152,000 36,152,500 36,153,000 36,153,500 36,154,000 36,154,500 36,155,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811
Putative 11-S seed storage protein, plant

CP18: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:36151945..36155113 Go

36,152,000 36,152,500 36,153,000 36,153,500 36,154,000 36,154,500 36,155,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811
Putative 11-S seed storage protein, plant

CP19: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185871

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:36179582..36195160 Go

36,180,000 36,182,500 36,185,000 36,187,500 36,190,000 36,192,500 36,195,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1R0202650

MtrunA17_Chr1g0185871
Putative glucosylceramidase

MtrunA17_Chr1g0185881
Putative Heat shock protein DnaJ, cysteine-

30
R0202640

CP20: MtrunA17_Chr1g0190571

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:39785399..39788859 Go

39,785,500 39,786,000 39,786,500 39,787,000 39,787,500 39,788,000 39,788,500

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0190571
Putative leucine-rich repeat-containing, plant-type, leucine-rich repeat domain superfamily

CP21: MtrunA17_Chr1g0191411

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr1" and "MtrunA17Chr1:40478958..40481594".

Coordinates: 479,000 40,479,500 40,480,000 40,480,500 40,481,000 40,481,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP22: MtrunA17_Chr1g0198091

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:45156990..45160317 Go

7,000 45,157,500 45,158,000 45,158,500 45,159,000 45,159,500 45,160,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0198091 hypothetical protein

MtrunA17_Chr1R024379 Putative glutathione transferase

CP23: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:46698414..46703228 Go

46,698,750

46,700,000

46,701,250

46,702,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 Putative protein-synthesizing GTPase

MtrunA17_Chr1R0250160

CP24: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:46698414..46703228 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071
Putative protein-synthesizing GTPase

MtrunA17_Chr1R0250160

CP25: MtrunA17_Chr1g0202001

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search. Search bar: MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:48254957..48258442 Go

255,000 48,255,500 48,256,000 48,256,500 48,257,000 48,257,500 48,258,000 48,258,500

1. Reference sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP26: MtrunA17_Chr1g0205601

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:50790395..50790919 Go

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0205601 Putative photosystem I PsuD

CP27: MtrunA17_Chr1g0207811

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:52230864..52236875 Go

52,231,250 52,232,500 52,233,750 52,235,000 52,236,250

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP28: MtrunA17_Chr1g0207921

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MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:52332410..52333430 Go

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP29: MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search box (MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:53642876..53643728 Go), and data source icons (CC BY-NC)

875 53,643,000 53,643,125 53,643,250 53,643,375 53,643,500 53,643,625

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791 ← Putative Zinc finger protein JAGGED/KNUCKLES

CP30: MtrunA17_Chr1g0210521

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr1" and "MtrunA17Chr1:54281237..54286625".

Coordinates: 1,250 54,282,500 54,283,750 54,285,000 54,286,250

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP31: MtrunA17_Chr1g0212961

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:55962093..55967938 Go

55,962,500 55,963,750 55,965,000 55,966,250 55,967,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr1

CP32: MtrunA17_Chr1g1004575

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr1 MtrunA17Chr1:53692370..53693062 Go

92,375 53,692,500 53,692,625 53,692,750 53,692,875 53,693,000

CP33: MtrunA17_Chr2g0283311

1. Reference sequence
sequence Zoom in to see sequence

CP34: MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr2" and "MtrunA17Chr2:5959685..5968666 (8)".

5,960,000 5,961,250 5,962,500 5,963,750 5,965,000 5,966,250 5,967,500 5,968,750

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP35: MtrunA17_Chr2g0292921

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a 'Go' button.

Search bar: MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:11820525..11825021

Track icons: CG, CHG, CHH

11,821,250 11,822,500 11,823,750 11,825,000

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP36: MtrunA17_Chr2g0298731

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000

MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:16645744..16665447 Go

16,650,000 16,655,000 16,660,000 16,665,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP37: MtrunA17_Chr2g0299561

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Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search

MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:17472150..17480276 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP38: MtrunA17_Chr2g0304891

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls (back, forward, zoom in, zoom out) and a search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr2' and 'MtrunA17Chr2:23443078..23451188'. Includes icons for CC, CNG, and CBE.

1. Reference sequence
see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP39: MtrunA17_Chr2g0305951

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MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:26442969..26443175 Go

26,443,000

26,443,050

26,443,100

26,443,150

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr2g0305951
putative protein

CP40: MtrunA17_Chr2g0309251

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

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Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out

MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:32020490..32027180

Go, Download, CC, CNG, CIRM

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP41: MtrunA17_Chr2g0310041

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Navigation controls including left and right arrows, zoom in (+) and zoom out (-) magnifying glasses, and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr2" and "MtrunA17Chr2:32954161..32955381".

MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:32954161..32955381 Go

Reference sequence track showing "1. Reference sequence" with a collapse icon. Below the track, the text "Zoom in to see sequence" is repeated across the width of the track.

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr2g0310041
Putative aconitate hydratase

CP42: MtrunA17_Chr2g0312631

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000

MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:35457593..35465666 Go

0 35,458,750 35,460,000 35,461,250 35,462,500 35,463,750 35,465,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr2g0312631
Putative minus-end-directed kinesin ATPase

CP43: MtrunA17_Chr2g0316291

Navigation controls including left and right arrows, zoom in/out magnifying glasses, a search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr2' and 'MtrunA17Chr2:38503432..38508154', a 'Go' button, and logos for CC, CNG, and CIRM.

1. Reference sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr2g0316291 Putative AAA-

CP44: MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801

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Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a 'Go' button.

MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:46521055..46532301

1. Reference sequence

to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801 putative protein

CP45: MtrunA17_Ch2g0328091

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000

MtrunA17Chr2 MtrunA17Chr2:47493121..47496322 Go

47,493,500 47,494,000 47,494,500 47,495,000 47,495,500 47,496,000

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP46: MtrunA17_Chr2g0329031

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Navigation controls including left and right arrows, zoom in (+) and zoom out (-) magnifying glasses, a dropdown menu showing 'MtrunA17Chr2', a search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr2:48115012..48121482', a 'Go' button, and icons for CG, CHG, and CHM tracks.

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP47: MtrunA17_Chr3g0079521

CP48: MtrunA17_Chr3g0083801

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1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP49: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091141

Navigation bar with zoom controls (back, forward, zoom in, zoom out) and search fields containing 'MtrunA17Chr3' and 'MtrunA17Chr3:12389214..12395017'. Includes icons for file operations and licenses (CC, BY, NC, ND).

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP50: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091671

Navigation controls including left and right arrows, zoom in/out icons, a search bar containing 'MtrunA17Chr3' and 'MtrunA17Chr3:13011981..13012186', and a 'Go' button. There are also icons for CC, CHG, and CHH.

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP51: MtrunA17_Chr3g0096421

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls and search fields. Search fields contain 'MtrunA17Chr3' and 'MtrunA17Chr3:20509023..20512683'. A 'Go' button is present. Below the search fields are icons for CC, CHG, and CHH.

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP52: MtrunA17_Chr3g0100221

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3:24929132..24930354 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr3g0100221
 Putative P-loop containing nucleoside triphosphate hydrolase

MtrunA17_Chr3R0168260
 Putative P-loop containing nucleoside triphosphate h

CP53: MtrunA17_Chr3g0102171

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP54: MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls (back, forward, zoom in, zoom out) and search input: MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3.29910353..29916673 Go. Includes icons for CC, CMG, and CIRM.

29,911,250 29,912,500 29,913,750 29,915,000 29,916,250

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP55: MtrunA17_Chr3g0110451

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

CP56: MtrunA17_Chr3g0113591

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3:35234328..35244734 Go

35,235,000 35,237,500 35,240,000 35,242,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP57: MtrunA17_Chr3g0124631

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a 'Go' button. The search bar contains 'MtrunA17Chr3' and 'MtrunA17Chr3:43324714..43337904'.

3,325,000 43,327,500 43,330,000 43,332,500 43,335,000 43,337,500

1. Reference sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP58: MtrunA17_Chr3g0127321

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3:45445103..45447021 Go

45,445,500 45,446,000 45,446,500 45,447,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr3g0127321
putative protein

MtrunA17_Chr3R0273050

CP59: MtrunA17_Chr3g0130671

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out

MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3:47767061..47773476 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr3g0130671 Putative amino acid transporter, transmembrane domain-containing protein

transmembrane domain-containing protein

CP60: MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761

MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3:51582608..51589872 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761
 Putative peptidase M41, AAA+ ATPase domain, ATPase, AAA-type, core, peptidase, FtsH

MtrunA17_Chr3R0303760
 DTX_singleton_family3632

CP61: MtrunA17_Chr3g0137391

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP62: MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

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Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr3" and "MtrunA17Chr3:55982179..55988607".

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP63: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

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0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3:57581120..57591178 Go

57,582,500 57,585,000 57,587,500 57,590,000

1. Reference sequence

to see sequence Zoom in to

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP64: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3:57581120..57591178 Go

57,582,500 57,585,000 57,587,500 57,590,000

1. Reference sequence

to see sequence Zoom in to

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP65: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr3 MtrunA17Chr3:57581120..57591178 Go

57,582,500 57,585,000 57,587,500 57,590,000

1. Reference sequence

to see sequence Zoom in to

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP66: MtrunA17_Chr3g1011650

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

Navigation controls including left/right arrows, zoom in/out, a search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr3' and 'MtrunA17Chr3:26567566..26568017', and a 'Go' button. License icons for CC, CNG, and CIRM are also present.

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP67: MtrunA17_Chr4g0000131

5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000 60,000,000

MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:120996..131507 (10.5

1. Reference sequence 122,500 125,000 127,500 130,000

Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

GgbAS1, MtrunA17_Chr4g0000131 Putative beta-amyrin synthase 620 3832

CP68: MtrunA17_Chr4g0000891

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:558257..558885 (630) Go

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr4g0000891 putative protein

CP69: MtrunA17_Chr4g0004721

CP70: MtrunA17_Chr4g0014251

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000 60,000,000

MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:11672610..11673047 Go

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP71: MtrunA17_Chr4g0022491

Navigation bar with zoom controls, search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr4', and coordinates 'MtrunA17Chr4:22222978..22229345'. Includes icons for CC, CNG, and CIRM.

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr4g0022491
Putative transcription factor ULT family

CP73: MtrunA17_Chr4g0034271

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000 60,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr4" and "MtrunA17Chr4:33946004..33946985".

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Annotations for MtrunA17_Chr4R0214230 (RLX_singleton_family230) and MtrunA17_Chr4g0034271 (Putative kinase C-like, phorbol ester/diacylglycerol-binding protein).

CP74: MtrunA17_Chr4g0034491

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

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MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:34097414..34114916 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP75: MtrunA17_Chr4g0037381

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000 60,000,000

MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:35994448..35998769 Go

35,995,000 35,996,250 35,997,500 35,998,750

1. Reference sequence

sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr4g0037381 Putative transcription factor CSD family

CP76: MtrunA17_Chr4g0040471

CP77: MtrunA17_Chr4g0055331

MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:48991180..48992162 Go

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr4g0055331 Putative FAS1 domain-containing protein

CP78: MtrunA17_Chr4g0059001

MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:51841603..51847135 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP79: MtrunA17_Chr4g0063201

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:54833659..54834508 Go

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP80: MtrunA17_Chr4g0070011

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000 60,000,000

MtrunA17Chr4 MtrunA17Chr4:59770278..59779255 Go

59,771,250 59,772,500 59,773,750 59,775,000 59,776,250 59,777,500 59,778,750

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP81: MtrunA17_Chr5g0393401

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr5g0393401
Histone deacetylase 9

MtrunA17_Chr5R0000260

MtrunA17_Chr5g0393411

MtrunA17_Chr5R0000270

MtrunA17_Chr5R0000280

MtrunA17_Chr5R0000260

CP82: MtrunA17_Chr5g0400181

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a dropdown menu showing 'MtrunA17Chr5'. A search bar contains 'MtrunA17Chr5:4613658..4621380 (7) Go'. There are also icons for CC, CMG, and CIRM.

13,750 4,615,000 4,616,250 4,617,500 4,618,750 4,620,000 4,621,250

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP83: MtrunA17_Chr5g0405061

Medicago truncatula A17 v5

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Navigation controls including left and right arrows, zoom in (+) and zoom out (-) icons, a dropdown menu showing 'MtrunA17Chr5', a text input field containing 'MtrunA17Chr5:8324045..8327123 (3)', and a 'Go' button.

Epigenetic marks icons: CG (Cytosine Methylation), CHG (H3K9me3), and CHH (H3K27me1).

1. Reference sequence
 Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP84: MtrunA17_Chr5g0408581

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in (+), zoom out (-), search (magnifying glass), and a 'Go' button.

Coordinates: MtrunA17Chr5 | MtrunA17Chr5:10628800..10633593 | 10,630,000 | 10,631,250 | 10,632,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Mtrun
Putat

CP85: MtrunA17_Chr5g0415031

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

Navigation controls: Home, Back, Forward, Search, Zoom in, Zoom out, MtrunA17Chr5, MtrunA17Chr5:15928882..15948476, Go, CC, CNG, CDM

Coordinates: 15,930,000 15,935,000 15,940,000 15,945,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP86: MtrunA17_Chr5g0415911

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Navigation controls including left and right arrows, zoom in (+) and zoom out (-) icons, a search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr5', and a 'Go' button. To the right are icons for file operations and a Creative Commons license logo.

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761

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1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP88: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291

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Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

MtrunA17Chr5 MtrunA17Chr5:23914525..23923967 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291

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Share

Navigation icons: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search

MtrunA17Chr5 MtrunA17Chr5:23914525..23923967 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP90: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341

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1. Reference sequence
see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP91: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

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MtrunA17Chr5 MtrunA17Chr5:31569352..31576930 Go

1. Reference sequence

see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP92: MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

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MtrunA17Chr5 MtrunA17Chr5:32286858..32292913 Go

1. Reference sequence

see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr5R0182100

MtrunA17_Chr5R0182110

MtrunA17_Chr5g0431411
hypothetical protein

MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401
Putative cyanohydrin beta-glucosyltransferase

CP93: MtrunA17_Chr5g0435191

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

1. Reference sequence

sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP94: MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

MtrunA17Chr5 MtrunA17Chr5:41737382..41743910 Go

41,737,500 41,738,750 41,740,000 41,741,250 41,742,500 41,743,750

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP95: MtrunA17_Chr6g0451601

Medicago truncatula A17 v5

File View Help

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1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP96: MtrunA17_Chr6g0452781

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

Navigation controls: Home, Back, Forward, Zoom In, Zoom Out, Search, Go, and social media icons (CC, CNG, CIRM).

Search bar: MtrunA17Chr6 MtrunA17Chr6:3110326..3118773 (8)

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP97: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457351

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

MtrunA17Chr6 MtrunA17Chr6:7086546..7089349 (2) Go

7,087,000 7,087,500 7,088,000 7,088,500 7,089,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

COX1, MtrunA17_Putative cytochrome

CP98: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP99: MtrunA17_Chrg0457461

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

RBCS-1, MtrunA17_Chrg0457461 Putative ribulose-bisphosphate carboxylase

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

RBCS-1, MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461
Putative ribulose-bisphosphate carboxylase

CP101: MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls (back, forward, zoom in, zoom out) and search fields: MtrunA17Chr6, MtrunA17Chr6:7692263..7697066 (4) Go

7,692,500 7,693,750 7,695,000 7,696,250

1. Reference sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

8,631,750 8,631,875 8,632,000 8,632,125

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP103: MtrunA17_Chr6g0461931

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5

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Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in (+), zoom out (-), search (magnifying glass), and a 'Go' button.

Search input: MtrunA17Chr6

Search results: MtrunA17Chr6:11048090..11050756

Additional icons: CC, CMG, CDM

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

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1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr6g0468411 Putative eukaryotic translation initiation factor 3 subunit C domain-containing protein

CP106: MtrunA17_Chr6g0476751

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

CP107: MtrunA17_Chr6g0479001

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search box (MtrunA17Chr6), coordinates (MtrunA17Chr6:33593736..33605210), Go button, and data source icons (CC, GNG, CHN).

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP108: MtrunA17_Chr6g0485321

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP109: MtrunA17_Chr6g0486961

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

MtrunA17Chr6 MtrunA17Chr6:41363320..41367612

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

← MtrunA17_Chr6R0258970

MtrunA17_Chr6g0486961
Putative protein kinase RLK-Pelle-LRR-XI-1 family

MtrunA17_Chr6R0258980
RLX_singleton_family341

CP110: MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls and coordinates: MtrunA17Chr7 MtrunA17Chr7:866304..873877 (7.5k) Go

0 867,500 868,750 870,000 871,250 872,500 873,750

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741
Putative transaldolase

CP111: MtrunA17_Chr7g0214911

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP112: MtrunA17_Chr7g0219691

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a search bar containing "MtrunA17Chr7".

Coordinates: 5,033,500 5,034,000 5,034,500 5,035,000 5,035,500 5,036,000 5,036,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP113: MtrunA17_Chr7g0221631

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search, MtrunA17Chr7 dropdown, MtrunA17Chr7:7209078..7210130 (1) Go, and license icons (CC, BY, NC, ND).

1. Reference sequence 7,209,250 7,209,500 7,209,750 7,210,000

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls and search box:

← → 🔍 🔍 🔍 🔍 MtrunA17Chr7 MtrunA17Chr7:16548292..16553149 Go 📄 📄 📄 📄

16,548,750 16,550,000 16,551,250 16,552,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP115: MtrunA17_Chr7g0230341

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

MtrunA17Chr7 MtrunA17Chr7:18998281..18998802 Go

18,998,375 18,998,500 18,998,625 18,998,750

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP116: MtrunA17_Chr7g0232851

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

MtrunA17Chr7 MtrunA17Chr7:23183074..23184387 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP117: MtrunA17_Chr7g0237331

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a 'Go' button.

Search input: MtrunA17Chr7 MtrunA17Chr7:27536059..27539723

Coordinates: 27,536,500 27,537,000 27,537,500 27,538,000 27,538,500 27,539,000 27,539,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP118: MtrunA17_Chr7g0251971

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search box containing 'MtrunA17Chr7', and a 'Go' button.

1. Reference sequence

MtrunA17_Chr7g0251971 putative protein

CP119: MtrunA17_Chr7g0259611

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr7 MtrunA17Chr7:44562558..44567283 Go

0 44,563,750 44,565,000 44,566,250

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP120: MtrunA17_Chr7g0262821

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

MtrunA17Chr7 MtrunA17Chr7:46824477..46828944 Go

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search box (MtrunA17Chr7), coordinates (MtrunA17Chr7:52366040..52373835), Go button, and icons for CC, CHG, CHH.

52,366,250 52,367,500 52,368,750 52,370,000 52,371,250 52,372,500 52,373,750

1. Reference sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP122: MtrunA17_Chr7g1034306

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000 50,000,000 55,000,000

MtrunA17Chr7 MtrunA17Chr7:55221249..55222325 Go

1,250 55,221,500 55,221,750 55,222,000 55,222,250

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP123: MtrunA17_Chr8g0338111

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence	Zoom in to see sequence						
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1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP125: MtrunA17_Chr8g0339891

1. Reference sequence

sequence Zoom in to see sequence

CP126: MtrunA17_Chr8g0342881

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in (-), zoom out (+), dropdown menu (MtrunA17Chr8), text input (MtrunA17Chr8:6296968..6303771 (6)), Go button, and icons for CG, CHG, CHM.

6,297,500 6,298,750 6,300,000 6,301,250 6,302,500 6,303,750

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP128: MtrunA17_Chr8g0353711

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP129: MtrunA17_Chr8g0355501

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000

MtrunA17Chr8 MtrunA17Chr8:17051718..17055744 Go

17,052,500

17,053,750

17,055,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in (+), zoom out (-), dropdown menu (MtrunA17Chr8), text input (MtrunA17Chr8:18171399..18175626), Go button, and icons for file operations and sharing.

Reference sequence track: 1. Reference sequence. Includes zoom controls and coordinates 18,172,500, 18,173,750, and 18,175,000.

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP132: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368731

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP133: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368931

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search box (MtrunA17Chr8, MtrunA17Chr8:32242116..32246400), Go button, and icons for genome browser and data sources.

32,242,500 32,243,750 32,245,000 32,246,250

1. Reference sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP134: MtrunA17_Chr8g0371281

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search. Search bar: MtrunA17Chr8 MtrunA17Chr8:34120414..34125650 Go. License icons: CC BY-NC-ND.

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP135: MtrunA17_Chr8g0371741

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000

MtrunA17Chr8 MtrunA17Chr8:34381623..34385029 Go

34,382,000 34,382,500 34,383,000 34,383,500 34,384,000 34,384,500 34,385,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP136: MtrunA17_Chr8g0373091

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

CP137: MtrunA17_Chr8g0376411

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5

File View Help

Share

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000

MtrunA17Chr8 MtrunA17Chr8:38012937..38018170 Go

38,013,750

38,015,000

38,016,250

38,017,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP139: MtrunA17_Chr8g0385331

7r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

0 5,000,000 10,000,000 15,000,000 20,000,000 25,000,000 30,000,000 35,000,000 40,000,000 45,000,000

MtrunA17Chr8 MtrunA17Chr8:44054508..44063565 Go

44,055,000 44,056,250 44,057,500 44,058,750 44,060,000 44,061,250 44,062,500

1. Reference sequence	sequence	Zoom in to see sequence						
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1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

MtrunA17_Chr8g0385331
Putative transcription factor C2H2 family

Navigation controls: left arrow, right arrow, zoom in, zoom out, search icon

MtrunA17Chr8 MtrunA17Chr8:49013922..49014338 Go

1. Reference sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence
to see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP142: MtrunA17_CPg0492381

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

0 10,000 20,000 30,000 40,000 50,000 60,000 70,000 80,000 90,000 100,000 110,000 120,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a dropdown menu showing 'MtrunA17CP'.

MtrunA17CP:25464..27963 (2.5 Kb) Go

Track icons: CG, CHG, CHH

25,500 26,000 26,500 27,000 27,500

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP143: MtrunA17_CPg0492461

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 10,000 20,000 30,000 40,000 50,000 60,000 70,000 80,000 90,000 100,000 110,000 120,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls (back, forward, zoom in, zoom out) and search box containing 'MtrunA17CP' and 'MtrunA17CP:30706..41202 (10.5 Kb)'. Includes icons for CG, CHG, CHM.

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence (repeated across the track)

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP144: MtrunA17_CPg0492851

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 10,000 20,000 30,000 40,000 50,000 60,000 70,000 80,000 90,000 100,000 110,000 120,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out

MtrunA17CP MtrunA17CP:62127..64710 (2.58 Kb) Go

CG, CHG, CHM tracks

62,500 63,000 63,500 64,000 64,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

petA, MtrunA17_CPg0492851
Putative cytochrome f, rudiment single hybrid, cytochrome f transmembrane anchor

MtrunA17_CPg0492861
hypothetical protein

cemA, MtrunA17_CPg0492871
Putative chloroplast envelope membrane protein,

CP145: MtrunA17_CPg0492941

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 10,000 20,000 30,000 40,000 50,000 60,000 70,000 80,000 90,000 100,000 110,000 120,000

MtrunA17CP MtrunA17CP:71549..74513 (2.97 Kb) Go

72,000 72,500 73,000 73,500 74,000 74,500

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP146: MtrunA17_CPg0493291

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search box (MtrunA17CP), dropdown menu (MtrunA17CP:106870..108224 (1.36)), Go button, and icons for CG, CHG, CHM.

1. Reference sequence
see sequence Zoom in to see sequence

CP147: MtrunA17_CPg0493401

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

0 10,000 20,000 30,000 40,000 50,000 60,000 70,000 80,000 90,000 100,000 110,000 120,000

Navigation icons: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out

MtrunA17CP MtrunA17CP:114947..117320 (2.38 kbp) Go

115,000 115,500 116,000 116,500 117,000

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

atpB, MtrunA17_CPg0493401
Putative H(+)-transporting two-sector ATPase

a/epsilon subunit, ATP synthase delta/epsilon subunit

rbcL, MtrunA17_CPg0493411
Putative ribulose-bisphosphate carboxylase

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence

Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP149: MtrunA17_MTg0490471

A17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 20,000 40,000 60,000 80,000 100,000 120,000 140,000 160,000 180,000 200,000 220,000 240,000 260,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls (back, forward, zoom in, zoom out), search box containing 'MtrunA17MT', and a 'Go' button. Additional icons for CG, CHG, and CHM are visible.

1. Reference sequence 56,500 57,000 57,500 58,000

Zoom in to see sequence (repeated five times across the track)

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help

Share

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

CP153: MtrunA17_MTg0491291

MtrunA17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 20,000 40,000 60,000 80,000 100,000 120,000 140,000 160,000 180,000 200,000 220,000 240,000 260,000

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search, MtrunA17MT, MtrunA17MT:178696..181324 (2.63 kbp), Go, CG, CHG, CHH

179,000 179,500 180,000 180,500 181,000

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

0 20,000 40,000 60,000 80,000 100,000 120,000 140,000 160,000 180,000 200,000 220,000 240,000 260,000

Navigation bar with zoom controls (back, forward, zoom in, zoom out), search box containing 'MtrunA17MT', and a 'Go' button. Additional icons for CG, CHG, and CHH are present.

Table with 6 columns and 1 row. Column 1: 208,750. Column 2: 210,000. Column 3: 211,250. Column 4: 212,500. Column 5: 213,750. Column 6: 215,000. Row 1: Zoom in to see sequence (repeated 6 times).

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP155: MtrunA17_MTg0491621

Medicago truncatula A17 v5 File View Help Share

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in/out, search box (MtrunA17MT), and download icons (CG, CHG, CHH).

1. Reference sequence
Zoom in to see sequence

1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

CP156: MtrunA17_MTg0491711

A17r5.0-ANR/jbrowse/current/?data=%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR%2Fjbrowse%2Fdata%2FMtrunA17r5.0-ANR&nav=1&t...

Navigation controls: back, forward, zoom in, zoom out, search, and a dropdown menu showing 'MtrunA17MT'.

MtrunA17MT:235762..243206 (7.45 kb)

Go button and track icons for CG, CHG, and CHM.

1. Reference sequence

sequence	Zoom in to see sequence					
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1.a. Complete annotation (EuGene/Repeats/Rescued), release 1.9

Supplementary Dataset S11. The genomic landscape at and around the primary-source loci of 156 MS-supported chimeric peptides. Each image represents a screenshot from the *Medicago truncatula* genome browser v. 5.1.7. Color codes for genes of different RNA types are shown below. Arrows pointing from left to right and in the opposite direction indicate loci that are located on the plus and minus strands, respectively.

- exons of mRNA genes
- introns of mRNA genes
- UTRs of mRNA genes
- ncRNA and tRNA genes
- rRNA genes
- pre-miRNA genes
- repeat elements